

THE EFFECT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE MEDIATED BY REMUNERATION IN STATE UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

The performance of education professionals at universities is critical to running university operations smoothly. This study aimed to see how the work environment affected employee performance as mediated by compensation. This study is explanatory. A convenience sample of 120 respondents from education personnel in state universities was selected using a convenience sampling approach. As a research instrument, questionnaires were given to education staff at state universities in South Sumatra. The partial least squares structural equation model (SEM-PLS) was used to examine the data. The findings revealed that the work environment considerably influenced salary but had no effect on employee performance. Furthermore, pay has a considerable impact on employee performance. Furthermore, the study's findings indicate that salary plays a complete mediating role in moderating the influence of the work environment on employee performance. It indicates that by optimizing compensation, the work environment will have a direct influence on increasing education personnel performance.

Keywords: Work Environment, Employee Performance, Remuneration.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are an important aspect of a company, agency or institution, especially those involved in managing, organizing, and using organizational components to achieve the goals that have been set (Matriadi et al., 2019). The quality of Human Resources (HR) who are competitive, according to their various talents, and have strong mental and personalities determines the success or decline of an organization inside a corporation. The productivity of each employee's performance influences an organization's success benchmark. Employee performance covers output quality, quantity, and dependability at work (Ridha et al., 2020). Employees may work well if they have excellent performance and can also generate a nice job. An employee's strong performance is intended to enable an organization's goals to be met as planned. Companies or institutions are constantly concerned with efforts to increase employee performance that result in work satisfaction for employees in order to meet business goals (Basher Rubel & Hung Kee, 2015). One approach is to enhance the working environment. Every firm will struggle to achieve its objectives if the surrounding atmosphere is deplorable, resulting in low staff morale and decreased job satisfaction.

The work environment of an agency must be carefully considered since it has a direct impact on personnel. A positive work environment can boost employee performance, whereas a negative work environment can lower employee performance. When humans can carry out

duties optimally, healthily, safely, and comfortably, the work environment is considered excellent. In the long run, the appropriateness of the work environment may be seen (Pawirosumarto et al., 2017). An unattractive work environment might necessitate more people and time, and it does not promote the development of an effective work system design (Wandari & Mujiati, 2021). The environment is an institution or external influence that can influence organizational performance. The environment is divided into two categories general and specific. (Syamsuddin et al., 2021). The work environment also influences employee performance. A nice work atmosphere is critical for increasing employee performance levels. The work environment is the full facility and infrastructure surrounding employees conducting work that can impact how their work is implemented (Astarina et al., 2021). The work environment includes all aspects, inside and outside the company, that directly or indirectly influence management operations to achieve an organization's goals (Parent-Lamarche, Marchand, and Saade, 2021). A nice and comfortable work atmosphere will influence an employee's performance and vice versa. If an employee's working environment is unpleasant, his or her performance will also suffer. Aside from the work environment, pay provision is also a component.

The pay program and job analysis, job assessment, and remuneration systems are part of the system structuring program. Job analysis is designed to analyze workload using assessment as a monitor, and the payment system is compensation for workload system architecture (Brahmannanda & Dewi, 2020). That is, there is no compensation without workload because remuneration is decided by the weight of the workload as established by the grades and job classes (job analysis). Employee motivation and performance can both benefit from remuneration or pay. It is because providing excellent compensation might motivate people to perform more. Compensation or prizes will increase job motivation, immediately boosting individual performance (Kusuma et al., 2018). Employees are supposed to be motivated and encouraged to be more professional and to enhance their performance due to remuneration. Employees will feel certain of their well-being if their demands are addressed, including economic (financial) needs, expressed in the employee's pay structure. As a result, it is necessary to change the incentive system to only focus on positions and education without considering employee performance for the company. According to (Tj et al., 2021), a compensation or payroll system is a payment and reward system for services performed by workers. The payment is made monthly, independent of the number of hours, working days, or items manufactured. The incentive system must be restructured to include a compensation or remuneration system based on employee performance (Durward et al., 2020). The government ensures a high level of welfare and preservation efforts for employees under this compensation scheme so that workers feel fulfilled and can focus on contributing to the organization's best performance (Berber et al., 2022). Furthermore, the appropriateness of pay or remuneration will have a favourable influence on employee performance. It will influence employee performance, which can be developed if employee performance improves, particularly in colleges.

Higher education is a key function and position in reaching macro education goals that require constant improvement efforts to actualize excellent human resources. Based on the facts in the

field thus far, universities must focus on optimizing the creation of a friendly work environment supported by adequate payment for their academic staff. The work atmosphere is critical for employees, and this compensation scheme fosters pleasant working circumstances (Setyadi et al., 2022). As a result, it has an impact on performance. Past study findings indicate a research gap on the impact of work environment and compensation on employee performance. According to a study (Haslina et al., 2014), the effect of the work environment and salary on job satisfaction is positive and considerable, as is the influence of employee performance mediated by employee job satisfaction. According to (Hutomo et al., 2020), the work environment has a good and substantial influence on employee performance. According to (Sudiarditha, 2019), pleasant working circumstances make employees feel safe and productive in carrying out their daily tasks or obligations. However, it differs from (Widiastutik, 2022), who claims that salary does not influence work satisfaction.

Compared to previous studies, the originality of this study is the inclusion of compensation as a moderating component. In the previous study, it was included as an independent variable along with the work environment variable. Furthermore, education professionals at public universities are the subject of the study. Based on the preceding description, this study will develop a suitable economic model based on empirical data concerning the role of pay in the effect of the work environment on the performance of educational people in state institutions. This study will also examine how the work environment affects the performance of education employees in public institutions, using salary as a mediator.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Environment

The work environment includes everything that surrounds employees and can interfere with their ability to do given activities, such as cleanliness, music, lighting, and so on. Clear job descriptions, demanding work objectives, effective work communication styles, a work atmosphere, and somewhat acceptable work facilities are all part of the work environment (Al-Omari & Okasheh, 2017). The work environment might include all of the equipment and materials encountered, as well as the environmental elements in which a person who works, his work practices, and work arrangements as individuals and groups. The work environment may also be viewed as a state connected to the effects of workplace features on employee behavior and attitudes, where it is associated to the development of psychological changes (Aronsson et al., 2017). This is encountered in their job that the company must consider, which includes work dullness, boring labor, and exhaustion. As a result, the work environment in this study is defined as anything that is surrounding employees at work, both physical and non-physical, that can impact employees at work. Employees can be safe and comfortable if the work environment is favorable, but employees cannot be safe and comfortable if the work environment is not supportive.

Work environment indicators (Linton et al., 2015) are as follows: 1) Work environment is the circumstance that occurs around employees who are conducting task that can impact how the work is done. This work environment will comprise the workplace, amenities and work aids,

cleanliness, illumination, tranquillity, and the working relationships among the individuals in the area. 2) Relationships with coworkers, specifically relationships with coworkers that are harmonious and free of mutual interest among coworkers. The amicable interaction between coworkers is one of the characteristics that might encourage employees to stay in one firm. One of the aspects that might influence employee performance is harmonious and family ties. 3) Work facility availability, which indicates that the equipment utilized to facilitate smooth operation is complete/up to date. Although not new, the provision of comprehensive work facilities is one of the equipment needed in functioning.

Remuneration

Remuneration technically means "payment" or "salary," but it can also refer to the distribution of money or the substitution of money set by particular laws as a reward for a task that is normal in nature, omitting overtime and honorariums (Aslam et al., 2019). Remuneration is a prize for services supplied by the firm to employee as a bonus for the company's accomplishments in attaining its goals. This knowledge demonstrates that its presence in the organization cannot be dismissed or overlooked since it is directly tied to the achievement of corporate goals (Bilan et al., 2017). Employees receive remuneration as a kind of recognition for their contributions to the organization. The remuneration indicators are (Kanapathippillai et al., 2016): 1) Restoration Salary, is a resource in the form of money that employers offer to staff in return for the thinking energy that has been supplied in order to fulfill the company's aims. 2) Rewards are direct prizes offered to employees for achieving or exceeding the specified objective in their work performance. 3) A benefit is an indirect or supplementary compensation delivered by the corporation to staff in the form of money or anything non-monetary. 4) Bonuses and incentives are awards given to employees by their employers or organizations for exceeding the expected outcomes or time frame. The bonus might be the shape of cash, pilgrimage, or something else. 5) Allowance is a regulated payment connected to work granted by an employer or firm to employees depending on their nature, set allowances, and non-permanent perks (Goh & Gupta, 2016).

Employee Performance

Performance is the outcome or degree of a person's success as a whole within a certain time in carrying out activities in comparison to work standards, objectives, or objectives that have been defined in advance and jointly (N et al., 2015). Performance or reform is a representation of the level of success achieved as a result of an activity policy or policy in attaining the organization's goals, objectives, and ambitions as described via strategic planning. Employee performance, expressed as output, efficiency, and effectiveness, is frequently linked to productivity (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2019). To accomplish that the organization works successfully and in accordance with the organization's goals, the organization must have strong employee performance, particularly by carrying out its obligations in a timely and efficient manner (Astarina et al., 2021). This work standard is compared by assessing the employee's performance using indicators or measuring scales developed by the agency. Performance assessment is one of the most essential criteria for businesses since it serves as the foundation for building a pay system for employees, which may impact the decision-making behavior of

leaders in the organization. (Pradhan & Jena, 2017) As a consequence, the performance in this research is the outcome of labor done by someone in an organization in order to fulfill an organization's intended goals while minimizing losses.

The following are employee performance indicators (Hermina & Yosepha, 2019): 1) Quantity is the amount produced represented in words such as the number of units or activity cycles performed. Employee views of the amount of allocated activities and their outcomes are used to calculate quantity. 2) Quality is defined as procedural adherence, discipline, and devotion. The degree to which the targeted activity outputs are near flawless in terms of adhering to some ideal style of executing the activity as well as reaching the activity's expected aims. The employee's impression of the quality of the work produced and the perfection of the job on the talents and abilities of employees are used to determine work quality. 3) Reliability is the capacity to do tasks with minimal supervision. Accuracy, true, and precise; dependability, which includes consistency of performance and dependability in service. 4) Capacity, working together refers to a workforce's ability to collaborate with others in order to complete a task and operate with optimal efficiency and effectiveness.

Hypothesis and research framework

A theoretical framework that defines the factors relating to product quality on brand image and its influence on purchasing decisions may be created based on the above description; the framework provided in this study is described in the figure below.

Figure 1. Research Framework

(Source: research model concept)

Based on the above model, the proposed hypothesis is as follows:

- H1: Work environment has a positive and significant effect on remuneration
- H2: Work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- H3: Remuneration has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

H4: Remuneration is a significant full mediator of the influence of work environment on employee performance

RESEARCH METHODS

This research design is in the form of explanatory research. Explanatory research is research used to explain causal relationships between variables through hypothesis testing, formulated or often referred to as explanatory research with a quantitative approach. This research is to see the effect of the work environment on employee performance mediated by remuneration. The variables of this study include the independent variable, namely Work Environment (X1), the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance (Y), and the moderator variable, namely Remuneration (Z). This study focuses on knowing whether there is an influence or relationship between the two variables consisting of the independent variable and the dependent variable.

The time of the research is from January 2022 to February 2022. This research population is education staff working at state universities in the province of South Sumatera. By using the convenience sampling technique, a sample of 120 respondents was selected. Determining the number of samples is also based on the minimum number of samples in the SEM analysis. There are 12 indicators in this study's three variables or constructs. One hundred twenty respondents make up the sample size. Instrumen yang digunakan berupa kuesioner yang disebar kepada dosen yang mengajar di perguruan tinggi negeri di provinsi sematera selatan. The type of questionnaire used in this study is a questionnaire paired with the type of scale used, namely the Likert scale (1-5) (Setyadi & Helmi, 2022). The grid of each variable is described in the following table.

Table 1. Grid of each Variable

Variables	Indicator	Item Code
Work Environment	Work atmosphere	X1
	Relationship with coworkers	X2
	Availability of work facilities	X3
Remuneration	Salary	Z1
	Incentive	Z2
	Benefits	Z3
	Bonuses and commissions	Z4
	Allowance	Z5
Employee Performance	Quality	Y1
	Quantity	Y2
	Is it reliable or not	Y3
	Cooperative Attitude	Y4

The structural equation modelling (SEM) data analysis approach was employed with the Smart PLS 3 software. A covariance matrix and analysis of variance were used to calculate SEM. SEM is used to solve multilevel models that cannot be solved concurrently using linear regression equations. Model specifications, an estimate of model parameters, structural model testing, and a demonstration of research hypotheses were the steps of PLS-SEM analysis in this work (Setyadi, Helmi, Ismail, et al., 2022). In PLS-SEM, model specification is accomplished by drawing a path diagram that depicts the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables (structural model) and the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables on their respective indicators. PLS-SEM evaluation of the measurement model creates non-parametric evaluation criteria and employs bootstrap and blinding processes (Setyadi, Helmi, & Hidayat, 2022). The measurement model assessment aims to assess the construct or measurement indicator's validity and reliability.

In this work, the reflecting measurement model was examined utilizing internal reliability (composite reliability), reliability indicators, and convergent validity (extracted mean variance). The greater the value of factor loadings on a build, the more similar the indications in the construct are. These features are known as indications of dependability. The value of factor loadings on all indicators must be significant statistically if it is less than 0.708. When the obtained outer loading value falls inside the 0.4-0.7 range, it must be regarded as eliminated from the model.

It should be noted that removing or removing these indicators from the model might raise the composite reliability score and the average variance extract (AVE). Generally, convergent validity may be measured using the AVE value, which must be more than 0.5. When the AVE value is more than 0.5, the concept describes more than half (50%) of each indicator's variation. If the AVE value is less than 0.5, the error is greater than the variation explained by the construct. The structural model is evaluated in steps, including collinearity testing, assessing the relevance of the connection to the structural model, and assessing T Value. The acceptable Critical Value must be less than 1.96. Then, examine the impact of the moderating variable, which causes the independent variable to influence the dependent variable. The T value is used to perform the test, and the allowable critical value must be larger than 1.96.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data Validity and Reliability Test

The average variance extract (AVE) was used to examine the validity of the questionnaire questions, and the instrument's accuracy was tested in a composites fashion, namely directly on the construct. The Construct Reliability (CR) price, dependent on the loading factor price, is used in this reliability test. The cost of each construct's validity and reliability index is displayed in the table below.

Table 2. AVE and CR Evaluation Value

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Category
Work Environment	0.872	0.922	0.797	Valid & Reliable
Remuneration	0.830	0.880	0.596	Valid & Reliable
Employee Performance	0.897	0.928	0.763	Valid & Reliable

According to Table 2, all variables have an AVE larger value than 0.50, confirming that the indicator reflects a produced and certified legitimate variable. If the Construct Reliability (CR) score is more than 0.80, then all concepts from this study may be incorporated into the model. Furthermore, Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.7 indicate that the instrument employed is exact and reliable in assessing each variable.

The goodness of the Fit Model Test

To test the hypotheses described earlier, a structural equation model was formed and tested in SmartPLS. The results of the structural model are described as follows.

Table 3. The goodness of fit test

Parameter Model	Saturated Model	Description
SRMR	0.079	Fit
d_ ULS	0.622	Fit
d_ G	0.297	Fit
Chi-Square	240.779	Fit
NFI	0.906	Fit

Table 3 displays the SEM results of the perfect fit model test. The graphic shows a structural model that has already fitted the fit specifications. These indicators (SRMR, d ULS, d G, Chi-square, and NFI) are good fits for all structures. According to him, the model must contain three to four indices in the excellent fit category to be considered practical or adequate. According to the fit test results, the overall research design has more than three indices in the region of outstanding fit.

The Model Estimation value is the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) model fit test. The value of the test results listed in the table above is 0.079, less than 0.08, which means this model is a goodness of fit measure for PLS-SEM, which can be used to avoid model misspecifications. d_ ULS (The Squared Euclidean Distance) and d_ G (The Geodesic Distance) that a good research model must have a value greater than 0.05 (because it uses a 95% confidence interval). It means that with the d_ ULS value of 0.622 and d_ G 0.297, the model in this study has a low residual distribution. A good Chi-Square value shows 2 Statistics < 2 Table, meaning that the number of manifest variables in the PLS path model and the number

of independent variables in the covariance matrix model is sufficient. The fit model results for the chi-square in this study amounted to 240.779, meaning that the two tables were smaller at 0.552 with a significance P-value of 0.05. It means that the number of manifest variables in the PLS path model and the number of independent variables in the covariance matrix model are fulfilled. Furthermore, it is supported by the study's Normal Fit Index (NFI) result of 0.906, which is larger than 0.9. Overall, it can be inferred that this structural model meets the fit requirements.

The results of the model test using SMART PLS, which includes the construction of each variable, can be seen in the previous hypotheses' structural model of work environment, remuneration, and employee performance. The structural model's results are described below.

Figure 2. Model Fit Estimate

(Source: SEM analysis results using Smart PLS)

Testing the Hypotheses: Structural Equation Models

Decisions based on the results of the descriptive analysis are certainly not convincing enough, but generally, they can provide an overview. It is necessary to test the data following the hypothesis proposed in this study. Hypothesis testing in SEM analysis is also known as structural model testing. Overall hypothesis testing for the tone variable's direct effect on another is seen in the following table.

Table 4. Summary of Hypothesis Tests on Relationships

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Result
H1	0.695	0.694	0.057	12.223	0.000	Significance
H2	0.095	0.077	0.118	0.803	0.422	Not Significance
H3	0.665	0.683	0.101	6.617	0.000	Significant

Note: *significant at critical ratio > 1.96.

Based on the results of the analysis from table 4, it is known that:

- Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on remuneration, with a t-value of $12.223 > 1.96$
- There is no positive and significant influence of Work Environment on Employee Performance; the t-value is $0.803 < 1.96$.
- Remuneration positively and significantly affects Employee Performance, with a t-value of $6.617 < 1.96$.

Table 4's findings indicating a considerable influence of the work environment on remuneration are backed by the findings of research undertaken by (Kusuma et al., 2018). His research demonstrated that a pleasant work environment influences pay. Furthermore, the data in table 4 contradict the conclusions of (Wijayanto, 2020) that the organizational work environment has a favourable and substantial influence on employee performance. It is due to the varied research items' cultures and environments. This study also supports the findings of (Martono et al., 2018) research showing that salary and work satisfaction has a beneficial influence on performance.

Testing mediation effects

One of the objectives of this research is to examine the mediating role of remuneration value on the effect of the work environment on employee performance. It is a complex mediating effect that includes many pathways for estimating. Indirect and total effects can be calculated from T Statistics or P Values. The results of the analysis can be seen in the table below.

Table 5. Mediation Effect

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
H4	0.462	0.477	0.093	4.960	0.000	Full Mediation

Note: *significant at critical ratio > 1.96.

Table 5 shows an indirect effect of work environment on employee performance mediated by remuneration with a value of $4.960 > 1.96$. So that the results of the mediation test can be concluded that remuneration has a full mediating effect so that the work environment can improve employee performance. Because the remuneration variable and work environment can determine employee performance will increase significantly. The model test findings support the link between work environment, compensation, and academic staff performance in state institutions. That is, this data supports the premise that if there is payment from the organization, in this case, state institutions, the work environment will significantly impact the education personnel. The study's findings will aid in producing practical implications for state institutions to improve the performance of education staff, who must pay attention to a

conditional work environment and payment. The findings of this study are corroborated by (Guritno et al., 2022), who found that a remunerated working environment considerably influences employee performance. Furthermore, research done by (Sitopu et al., 2021) indicates that salary functions as a full mediator on the influence of the work environment on job satisfaction. On the other hand, the work environment has little impact on employee performance without compensation. It demonstrates how important the link between these three variables essential.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings revealed that hypotheses 1, 3, and 4 were verified, while hypothesis 2 was not. According to the findings of hypothesis testing, the work environment has a considerable impact on pay. The work environment, on the other hand, has no discernible influence on employee performance. However, salary has a considerable impact on employee performance. Researchers successfully demonstrated that salary plays a substantial role as a mediator in the impact of the work environment on employee performance in this study. It indicates that pay for education staff will influence the work environment to enhance employee performance. Because it will be a proposal for improvement in enhancing the performance of education professionals, the consequences of this research will be extremely beneficial in increasing the quality of higher education services. However, this study has certain limitations, including the sampling procedure and the number of samples used. The researcher agrees that the more samples utilized, the more free of study bias the conclusions are and the more correctly they can be extrapolated. Recommendations for further study on the work environment model that influences the performance of education professionals at state universities, mediated by remuneration in trials in various locations with diverse objects. Not only does it have an impact on customer service quality, but it also has an impact on brand equity, customer loyalty, and employee loyalty. This research also recommends how to improve pay provision because it has been shown to affect the performance of education staff at public institutions.

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